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Laboratory sequencing protocols

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BioProject Advanced

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BioProject record linked from the raw sequence record in previous step

Links from SRA

Autonomous Reef Monitoring Structures (ARMS) in Poland in the framework of ARMS-MBON programme Accession: PRJEB37755 ID: 7241

Autonomous Reef Monitoring Structures (ARMS) in Poland

Study on the Autonomous Reef Monitoring Structures (ARMS) in Poland in the framework of ARMS-MBON programme. More...

Accession	PRJEB37755
Scope	Monoisolate
Publications	Daraghme N <i>et al.</i> , "A Long-Term Ecological Research Data Set From the Marine Genetic Monitoring Program ARMS-MBON 2018-2020.", <i>Mol Ecol Resour</i> , 2025 May;25(4):e14073
Submission	Registration date: 23-Apr-2021 HELLENIC CENTRE FOR MARINE RESEARCH

NAVIGATE UP

This project is a component of the European ARMS programme (ARMS-MBON)

NAVIGATE ACROSS

13 additional projects are components of the European ARMS programme (ARMS-MBON)

Open-access paper on PMC links to the lab sequencing protocols in supplementary information S1.

Paper found via web search:

from Obst *et al.* (2020). Fieldwork and sample processing for samples of this first data release followed the official ARMS-MBON Handbook v2.0, which is in parts based on the initial protocols developed by the Global ARMS Program

(<https://naturalhistory.si.edu/research/global-arms-program>). We used molecular protocols available under the ARMS-MBON Molecular Standard Operating Procedure v1.0 (MSOP). The Handbook and MSOP can be accessed on the ARMS-MBON GitHub repository (see Table S1 for links). Preserved replicates of the material samples are stored and

URL: <https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC11969632/>

Data Availability Statement

All data presented in this manuscript are publicly available, see main text and [Supporting Information](#) for detailed descriptions. Standard operating procedures and protocols are available on the dedicated ARMS-MBON GitHub repository (<https://github.com/arms-mbon/documentation>). All metadata and access to all image data generated by ARMS-MBON to date can be found on GitHub (https://github.com/arms-mbon/data_workspace). All genetic raw data generated by ARMS-MBON to date can be accessed on the European

[documentation](#) / [standard_operating_procedures](#) /

kmexter Update README.md ×

URL: https://github.com/arms-mbon/documentation/tree/main/standard_operating_procedures

Name	Last commit message
..	
ARMS_MolecularSOPs_v1.0.docx	changed folders to
ARMS_MolecularSOPs_v1.0.pdf	changed folders to
Global_ARMS_protocols.zip	Apply automatic c
README.md	Update README.r

Based on the PMC paper text, "MolecularSOPs_v1.0" in this GitHub documentation repository was used for lab sequencing protocols

Purpose

This document contains the Standard Operating Procedures for working with the molecular data of the ARMS-MBON (www.arms-mbon.eu) project. The samples containing the material are sent by each observatory to HCMR for processing (see the [Handbook](#) for details).

URL: https://github.com/arms-mbon/documentation/blob/main/standard_operating_procedures/ARMS_MolecularSOPs_v1.0.pdf

DNA Extraction

This protocol is used for each of the three ARMS fractions (motile 100µm – 500µm, motile 500µm – 2mm, and sessile).

Materials:

- Falcon tubes containing the samples stored in DMSO
- DNA-extraction kit (DNeasy PowerSoil Kit or DNeasy PowerSoil Pro Kit)
- Sterile pipettes and pipette tips
- DNA-decontaminating solution
- agarose/EtBr gel and loading buffer

From an OBIS occurrence record, we must follow 5 links / IDs to get to the sequencing protocol. (OBIS → SRA → Bioproject → PMC article → ARMS-MBON GitHub → Molecular SOPs document)

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Sample data

OBIS sample occurrence record → NCBI BioSample

```
"id": "00b278e2-1cb5-4a12-be99-ee8b4ffea9b7",
"identificationReferences": "PEMA v2.1.4 https://github.com/harisz",
"identificationRemarks": "RDP classifier; confidence cutoff 0.8; r",
"institutionCode": "ARMS-MBON",
"kingdom": "Animalia",
"kingdomid": 2,
"locationID": "Zatoka Pucka (http://marineregions.org/mrgid/29088)",
"marine": true,
"materialSampleID": "ARMS_Gdynia_GDY1_20190619_20191029_MF100_r1",
"maximumDepthInMeters": 4,
```

URL: <https://obis.org/occurrence/00b278e2-1cb5-4a12-be99-ee8b4ffea9b7>

Based on material sample ID, biosample record can be found via web search:

NIH National Library of Medicine
National Center for Biotechnology Information

URL: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/biosample/SAMEA14201105>

BioSample Advanced

Full ▾

ARMS_Gdynia_GDY1_20190619_20191029_MF100

Identifiers BioSample: SAMEA14201105; SRA: ERS11803981

Organism [marine metagenome](#)
unclassified entries; unclassified sequences; metagenomes; ecological metagenomes

Attributes

collection date	2019
geographic location	Poland
latitude and longitude	54.48522 N 18.57111 E
sample name	ARMS_Gdynia_GDY1_20190619_20191029_MF100
ENA first public	2022-04-21
ENA last update	2022-04-21
ENA-CHECKLIST	ERC000011
External Id	SAMEA14201105
INSDC center alias	HELLENIC CENTRE FOR MARINE RESEARCH
INSDC center name	HELLENIC CENTRE FOR MARINE RESEARCH
INSDC first public	2022-04-21T00:32:30Z
INSDC last update	2022-04-21T00:32:30Z
INSDC status	public
Submitter Id	ARMS_Gdynia_GDY1_20190619_20191029_MF100
environmental sample	Yes
geographic location (region and locality)	Gdynia

Sample type, collection date, location

No identifying person for the material sample.